

Improving Children's Digital Literacy: A Quantitative Study on the Use of Digital Storybooks in Elementary Schools

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ABSTRAK

Peserta didik di sekolah dasar berada dalam fase perkembangan yang krusial, dimana mereka mulai terpapar dengan berbagai jenis media digital. Pada fase ini, penting untuk memperkenalkan media belajar yang dapat memotivasi peserta didik untuk meningkatkan kemampuan literasi digital. Salah satu media belajar tersebut adalah buku cerita digital. Buku cerita digital memiliki tampilan yang lebih menarik jika dibandingkan dengan buku cerita cetak. Tujuan dari penelitian ini adalah untuk mengetahui pengaruh buku cerita digital terhadap literasi digital peserta didik di sekolah dasar. Metode yang digunakan dalam penelitian ini adalah quasi experiment dengan desain nonequivalent control group. Sampel penelitian terdiri dari 90 peserta didik kelas IV SD. Kelompok eksperimen dalam penelitian ini menggunakan buku cerita digital, sedangkan kelompok kontrol menggunakan buku cerita cetak. Teknik pengumpulan data menggunakan tes dalam bentuk soal pilihan ganda. Analisis data dilakukan dengan teknik analisis deskriptif dan uji Independent Sample t-test. Hasil uji hipotesis menggunakan Independent Sample t-test menunjukkan nilai signifikansi sebesar 0.000 (<0.05), artinya peserta didik di kelas eksperimen yang diberi perlakuan menggunakan buku cerita digital memiliki kemampuan literasi digital lebih baik dibandingkan peserta didik di kelas kontrol yang menggunakan buku cerita cetak. Sehingga dapat disimpulkan bahwa buku cerita digital berpengaruh terhadap literasi digital peserta didik di sekolah dasar.

ABSTRACT

Students in elementary school are in a crucial phase of development, where they are beginning to be exposed to various types of digital media. In this phase, it is important to introduce learning media that can motivate students to improve their digital literacy skills. One of the learning media is digital storybooks. Digital storybooks have a more attractive appearance when compared to printed storybooks. The purpose of this study is to determine the influence of digital storybooks on the digital literacy of students in elementary schools. The method used in this study is a quasi-experiment with a non-equivalent control group design. The research sample consisted of 90 students in grade IV of elementary school. The experimental group in this study used a digital storybook, while the control group used a printed storybook. The data collection technique uses a test in the form of multiple-choice questions. Data analysis was carried out using descriptive analysis techniques and the Independent Sample t-test test. The results of the hypothesis test using the Independent Sample t-test showed a significance value of 0.000 (<0.05), meaning that students in the experimental class who were treated using digital storybooks had better digital literacy skills than students in the control class who used printed storybooks. So, it can be concluded that digital storybooks have an effect on the digital literacy of students in elementary school.

1. INTRODUCTION

Education in the 21st century has undergone significant changes when compared to the previous century. The development of various branches of science and technology has a positive impact on the world of education, by providing unlimited information as if the world no longer has a dividing divide. The 21st century, which is characterized by advances in technology and information, is a hope in improving the quality of education in Indonesia. The education system is required to prepare students who are ready to face future challenges (Cahya et al., 2023; Rawung et al., 2021). Various technological advances have been

implemented to support the efficiency of education in Indonesia, one of which is by integrating technology into learning (Arikarani & Amirudin, 2021; Sinaga, 2023). Technological developments have now entered the stage of digital technology. The development of digital technology has brought significant changes in various aspects of life, including in the field of education. The digital era requires every individual to have good digital literacy skills. Digital literacy is an essential skill in the era of the Industrial Revolution 4.0 (Aoun, 2017; Febliza & Okatariyani, 2020; Hendaryan et al., 2022). Improving the quality of education starting from basic education is the key to facing the Industrial Revolution Era 4.0 (Anggraeni et al., 2019; Lase, 2016). Therefore, digital literacy learning in elementary schools is very important. Children of primary school age must have skills in understanding, interpreting, and utilizing information in digital format to face the challenges of modern education.

The concept of digital literacy was first introduced by Gilster in his book "Digital Literacy" in 1997. Gilster defines digital literacy as the ability to understand and apply information in various formats from various sources presented through computer technology (Nasrullah et al., 2017; Urip Umayah & Riwanto, 2020). Digital literacy refers to the ability to understand data in digital format (Buckingham, 2020; Nurjanah et al., 2017). Digital literacy is defined by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) as the ability to acquire, organize, digest, integrate, communicate, assess, and produce information using digital media in a safe and accurate way (Hidayati et al., 2020; Nurdina, 2022). Digital literacy is a must-have skill in the 21st century (Reddy et al., 2020; Wrahatnolo & Munoto, 2018). To understand the concept of digital literacy itself, it is necessary to look at it as a combination of various sub-themes including e-learning, information literacy and technology awareness all of which contribute to learning for the development of useful skills (Wilson et al., 2018; Yefanov et al., 2020). Digital literacy can also be interpreted as the ability to control the digital world through reading, writing, technical skills, and critical thinking in the use of technology to find, evaluate, and communicate information (Fraillon et al., 2020; Marsh, 2016). Digital literacy is the ability to use information and communication technology such as computers, the internet, and other digital devices (Islami et al., 2021; Liang et al., 2021).

Digital literacy is a provision for students to face challenges in the future. Digital literacy is an important skill that must be mastered at this time, where students are already closely related to digital media (Achmad & Utami, 2023; Moore & Trysnes, 2021). Digital literacy not only includes the ability to use digital devices, but also the ability to understand, evaluate, and process information obtained from various digital sources (Pangrazio et al., 2020; Wusqo et al., 2021). Digital literacy is the knowledge and skill of using digital media, communication tools, or networks to process information in a healthy, meticulous, and appropriate way (Naila et al., 2021; Roll & Ifenthaler, 2021). These skills are essential for the younger generation to actively and productively participate in the digital society. Digital literacy is an essential skill in the modern era that must be possessed by every individual, including children at the basic education level. Primary education has a strategic role in building a strong digital literacy foundation for elementary school-age children, because elementary school-age children are beginning to be exposed to various types of digital media (Bayu Ambarsari, 2023; Kuntarto & Prakash, 2020). This directly affects the way they obtain information and communicate. With the ease of accessing various types of digital media, students are increasingly open to new things outside their world. The ease of accessing various types of digital media should go straight to the digital literacy skills possessed by students, so that students can become wise people in using technology (Mardiana et al., 2022; Putu & Arima, 2024).

Learning digital literacy is not only learning about a theory, but students must process the learning through their cognitive performance. (Nurfaizah et al., 2022; Wijaya et al., 2016). The importance of digital literacy for elementary school children is even more urgent considering that they are at a crucial stage of cognitive and social development. Digital literacy helps students in elementary schools to hone their ability to use digital devices and know the concepts of ethics and security in using digital media (Devi Widiyanti et al., 2024; Mukhlisina & Danawati, 2023). Good digital literacy skills equip elementary school-age children to face challenges and opportunities in the digital era (Andriyani et al., 2023; Naimah et al., 2024). They will get used to participating positively in the digital space, understanding information critically, and even preventing the spread of hoaxes. Therefore, the world of education needs to teach digital literacy to students to build a better character for the nation's successors (Chan et al., 2017; Urip Umayah & Riwanto, 2020).

However, based on observations made in five elementary schools in Adiwerna District, only one school teaches digital literacy. There are several factors that cause digital literacy to be rarely taught in elementary schools. The lack of adequate facilities is one of the challenges to introduce digital literacy to students (Setiawan et al., 2023; Toharudin et al., 2021). The next factor is the gap in access and use of digital media (Achmadi et al., 2024; Putu & Arima, 2024). Not all children have easy access to digital media, so only a few children have good digital literacy skills. The lack of attention to introduce digital literacy to students in elementary school has an impact on students' digital literacy skills which still need to be improved (Isma et al., 2022; Yusniati et al., 2023). Based on interviews that have been conducted in grade IV of SDN Ujungrusi, most students only know digital media to play games, send messages or watch videos. Some

students know that digital media can be used as a means of learning, but rarely use it. In fact, if you can make optimal use of digital media, the existence of smartphones or laptops can be a source of learning for students (Abdullah & Wicaksono, 2020; Utami & Asri Hardini, 2021). This inequality shows the urgency to integrate contextual and interesting digital learning media in learning to improve children's digital literacy skills from an early age.

One of the potential learning innovations in improving children's digital literacy at elementary school age is the use of digital storybooks. Digital storybooks offer more interactive learning, so that through the use of digital storybooks, students can hone their digital literacy abilities in elementary schools (Polizzi, 2020; Shiyamsyah & Yuliani, 2022). Learning that is packaged using digital storybooks allows learners to more easily understand the content of reading through a more enjoyable learning experience (Neumann & Merchant, 2022; Zaidi et al., 2022). By integrating digital technology in learning, it is hoped that it can improve students' digital literacy skills. Digital storybooks are an innovation in learning that combines narrative text with interactive multimedia elements. This format has the potential to attract students who are already familiar with digital devices. In addition, the involvement of interactive elements can also strengthen cognitive and critical skills in processing digital information (Wangid et al., 2021; Zipke, 2017). Digital storybooks can also be a fun medium for elementary school students to spark interactive discussions (Solfiah et al., 2020; Zaidi et al., 2022).

Digital storybooks are often referred to as electronic storybooks. Basically, digital storybooks or electronic storybooks are the same thing, because both use digital devices (Gemala Qurbani, 2022; Nurhayati, 2017). Digital storybooks can contain different types of stories, from fiction to nonfiction and often include multimedia elements such as images, audio, or video to enhance the reading experience (Astriyandi, 2016; Tsuei et al., 2020). The digital storybook for elementary school students consists of five parts, namely the cover, leaflet, title page, content and back cover. In addition to unique images, the same theme allows images and text to blend perfectly and have unique artistic expressions, with images and words suitable for learning (Xiang & Yan, 2020; Zipke, 2017). The addition of interactive media such as educational games in digital storybooks is also needed, because educational games can foster critical thinking skills and increase students' interest in learning (Fitriyadi & Wuryandani, 2021; Rochmiyati et al., 2024). In addition, the educational games contained in the digital storybook are also in accordance with the characteristics of students in elementary schools who like to play.

The use of digital storybooks can expand students' insights and knowledge. Through gadgets, students can access a variety of book titles from various genres, topics, cultures, and countries. This diversity of content enriches students' knowledge and insight about the world. Students become more open to new things outside their world. The application of digital storybooks has a positive effect on creating a literacy culture among students. One of the methods that can be used to improve literacy culture among students is to apply digital books to the educational environment (Haslinda et al., 2022; Jauhari, 2021). The interesting features possessed by digital storybooks make students enjoy reading books more. Digital books with a good display and content that suits the needs of readers will help foster a literacy culture (Elsola & Rochmiyati, 2023; Nurchaili, 2016). The selection of digital books as a reading source is considered appropriate, because digital books can be used as a solution to improve digital literacy (Fitriyanti, 2021; Shiyamsyah & Yuliani, 2022). The more often students use digital media, it can improve students' digital literacy skills so that they are skilled in using technology to get information (Djonov et al., 2021; Rofiah et al., 2024). Through digital storybooks, students know that technology can be a fun learning medium and not just entertainment. Previous studies said that digital picture storybook media has been proven to improve the digital literacy skills of children aged 4-5 years (Neumann & Merchant, 2022; Rizkiyah, 2022). However, research that specifically examines the influence of digital storybooks on children's digital literacy skills at elementary school age is still limited.

This study presents a novel contribution to the field of elementary education and digital literacy by quantitatively examining the impact of digital storybooks on young learners' digital competencies, an area that remains underexplored in current literature. While previous research has largely emphasized the benefits of digital storybooks in fostering reading comprehension and language acquisition, this study uniquely centers on their role in enhancing children's digital literacy skills—such as navigating digital platforms, evaluating digital content, and developing responsible digital behavior. By employing a robust quantitative approach across multiple elementary school contexts, this research provides empirical evidence that bridges the gap between early literacy development and the cultivation of 21st-century digital skills. Furthermore, the study highlights the pedagogical potential of integrating multimedia narratives in everyday classroom instruction to support not only cognitive development but also the digital readiness of elementary students, which is critical in today's increasingly digital learning environments. This study aims to analyze the influence of the use of digital storybooks on the digital literacy skills of students in elementary schools. By using a quantitative approach and experimental methods, this study is expected to provide empirical evidence regarding the effectiveness of digital storybooks in improving children's digital literacy skills. The results of this research are expected to be a reference for educators in designing more effective

learning strategies and contributing to the development of digital technology-based education policies. Thus, this research not only contributes to enriching academic studies on digital literacy, but also provides practical solutions for teachers and policy makers in improving the quality of learning in the digital era. This research is expected to be the first step in developing a more inclusive and effective digital-based learning ecosystem in elementary schools.

2. METHOD

This research will use a quantitative approach with the type of all-experiment research or quasi experiment. The research design to be used is a non-equivalent control group design. Pretest and posttest are used as empirical evidence of the results of the comparison between the experimental class and the control class. In this study, the researcher did not create new classes but used the classes as they are. There are two classes used in this study, namely the experimental class which is treated using a digital storybook, while in the control class the treatment is carried out using a printed storybook. The research was conducted at an elementary school located in Adiwerna District, Tegal Regency with the research subjects of students in grade IV of elementary school. Samples were taken using the purposive sampling technique. Sampling using the purposive sampling technique is due to the breadth of the research area and there are certain considerations related to the research, including (1) schools that have habituated literacy activities, (2) there are adequate facilities such as libraries and projectors, (3) the availability of internet networks in the area, (4) teacher qualifications and (5) participant characteristics educate. The results of the election were obtained from four elementary schools, namely SDN Ujungrusi 03, SDN Tembok Kidul 01, SDN Tembok Banjaraan 01 and SDN Ujungrusi 01.

The schools were chosen because they had criteria to represent the population. If the population is more than 1000, a sample of 10% is needed to be representative of the population (Kurniawan & Puspitaningtyas, 2016). Of the four schools, there are two schools that are the control group and the other two schools are the experimental group. The selection of the experimental class and the control class is also based on several considerations. Schools with the type of experimental classroom treatment have more adequate facilities, more active student characteristics and also teacher qualifications in using digital media. The data of the research sample is in the following Table 1.

Table 1. Research Sample Table

No	School Name	Type of Treatment	Number of students
1.	SDN Tembok Kidul 01	Experimental class	20
2.	SDN Ujungrusi 01	Experimental class	26
3.	SDN Ujungrusi 03	Control class	21
4.	SDN Tembok Banjaraan 03	Control class	23
Total			90

The data collection technique used in this study is a test to measure students' understanding and digital literacy skills. The test was carried out twice, namely before the treatment (pretest) and after the treatment (posttest). The main instrument used in this study is a digital literacy test to measure the level of digital literacy of students before and after treatment, covering aspects of understanding digital information, the ability to search and evaluate information, and digital communication skills. The digital literacy indicators used in this study are adapted from the digital competency profiles of students in Indonesia written by (Widiputera, 2021) and published by the Puslitjak, Balitbang & Books of the Ministry of Education and Culture. The indicators used are adjusted to the characteristics of students at the elementary school level who are just learning about digital literacy. The following is a grid of digital literacy instruments used in this study.

This research was carried out in several stages, the first is the preparation stage. At this stage, the researcher prepares research instruments, validates instruments, and selects research samples. Furthermore, the researcher gave an initial test to both groups to find out the initial ability of students' digital literacy. After knowing the initial ability of students' digital literacy, the researcher gave treatment. The experimental group was given learning using digital storybooks for 4 weeks, while the control group used printed storybooks. After that, the final test was given to find out the final ability of students' digital literacy after treatment. The last stage is data analysis to see significant differences between the experimental and control groups. The collected data was analyzed using normality tests and homogeneity tests to ensure the data met the assumptions of parametric statistics. Furthermore, the Independent Sample t-Test test was used to measure the difference in pretest and posttest results between the experimental and control groups. In addition, descriptive analysis is used to analyze data by describing or describing data that has been obtained from pretest and posttest results in experimental and control classes. The descriptive

analysis in this study was carried out by making a summary of the distribution of pretest and posttest data from the descriptive statistical results of the experimental class and the control class.

Table 2. Digital Literacy Test Instruments Grid

No	Indicator	Question Number	
		Pretest	Postest
1.	The ability of students to use digital tools and information.	1, 2, 5, 11, 13, 17, 19	1, 4, 7, 11, 14, 15, 20
2.	The ability of learners to protect themselves and others in cyberspace.	4, 12, 14, 15,	10, 12, 13, 16
3.	The ability of students to interact, engage, and influence in society positively and fairly by using ICT	7, 8, 20, 10	3, 5, 9, 18
4.	The ability of learners to recognize, navigate, and express emotions in digital interactions both intrapersonal and interpersonal.	3, 6, 9	6, 8, 2
5.	The ability of students to express and explore through content creation using ICT tools.	16, 18	17, 19
Number of questions		20	20

The use of early condition data in learning is to find out the initial picture of the digital literacy skills of grade IV children in both groups. Meanwhile, the final condition data was obtained to describe the influence of digital storybooks on students' digital literacy skills. The Independent Sample t-Test is used to determine whether there is a positive and significant influence of the bound variable on the partially independent variable. The basis for decision-making is if the sig value is < 0.05, then the independent variable has a positive and significant effect on the partially independent variable. The success of this study was measured based on the increase in students' digital literacy scores from pretest to posttest with significant differences between the experimental group and the control group.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Result

Before conducting a hypothesis test, the data from the pretest and posttest results are tested for normality to ensure that the distribution of data in the study follows the normal distribution. This is important to know because it is related to the accuracy of the selection of statistical tests to be used. The normality test calculation was carried out with the help of SPSS 27 for windows. The normality test was carried out using Kolmogorov-Smirnov. The selection of the test using Kolmogorov-Smirnov was because the number of samples in this study exceeded 50 students, namely a total of 91 students. The data is said to be normal if the significance is greater than 0.05 (>0.05), while the data is said to be abnormal if the signification is less than 0.05 (<0.05). Based on the normality test that has been carried out, the control group obtained a significance value of 0.145 before being treated, while after being given treatment, it obtained a significance value of 0.196. The experimental class on digital literacy data obtained a significance value of 0.200 both untreated and after being treated, so it can be said that the above data is normally distributed. The results of the normality test in this study can be seen in the following Table 3.

Table 3. Normality Test Table

Group	Type of Treatment	Kolomogorov-Smirnov		
		Statistic	df	Sig.
Control	Pretest	118	44	0.145
	Postest	113	44	0.196
Experiment	Pretest	104	46	0.200
	Postest	105	46	0.200

The homogeneity test carried out in this study used the levene test. The homogeneity test was carried out to determine whether the data had similarities (homogeneity) between the data groups of the research population. The data can be said to be homogeneous if it gains significance of more than 0.05 (>0.05). The results of the homogeneity test that have been carried out show that the data in this study are homogeneous, because the two variables obtained a signification value of more than 0.05 (>0.05). The results of the homogeneity test can be seen in the following Table 4.

Table 4. Homogeneity Test Table

Parameters Statistics		Statistik Levene	Df1	Df2	Sig.
Digital Literacy	Based on Mean	2.242	3	176	0.85
	Based on Media	2.152	3	175	0.95
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	2.152	3	165.872	0.96
	Based on trimmed mean	2.196	3	176	0.90

Based on the previous prerequisite test, it is known that the data is normally distributed and homogeneous. The next step is to test the hypothesis. The hypothesis test used in this study uses an independent sample t-test, the purpose of which is to find out the difference in the average number of reading interest and digital literacy scores both before and after being treated. The basis for decision-making in the independent sample t-test is the value of sig. < 0.05, then H_0 is rejected and H_α is accepted. The independent sample t-test is used to test the following hypotheses. H_0 = There is no positive and significant influence of the use of digital storybooks on digital literacy. H_α = There is a positive and significant influence of the use of digital storybooks on digital literacy. The paired sample t-test test data is presented in the following Table 5.

Table 5. Paired Sample t-test Table

Variabel	Group	N	Mean	Standar Deviasi	Sig. (2-tailed)
Digital Literacy	Experiment	46	65.35	19.509	0.000
	Control	44	50.23	18.519	0.000

From the Table 5, it can be seen that the data presented for the digital literacy variable, obtained an average of 63.35 in the experimental group and an average of 50.23 in the control group. The results of the Independent Samplet-test showed a significance value of 0.000 for the digital literacy variable. This means that in the second hypothesis, H_0 is rejected and H_α is accepted. The results showed that there was a difference in the average acquisition of digital literacy skills between students in the experimental and control groups. Therefore, the results of hypothesis testing in the study show that there is an influence of digital storybooks on students' reading interest and digital literacy.

Discussion

Technological advances have revolutionized the way we access information in learning. The ease of accessing information should be balanced with digital literacy skills. Digital literacy is a skill in processing information from digital media effectively and efficiently for use in learning and daily life (Andhany & Maysarah, 2023; Beck et al., 2021; Liang et al., 2021). Digital literacy is not only about skills in using digital devices, but also includes motor, cognitive and emotional skills (Helsper & Smahel, 2020; Nisa et al., 2023). Digital literacy is a basic skill in utilizing and producing digital media (Andriyani et al., 2023; Harjono et al., 2019) In today's all-digital era, digital literacy is a very important skill for every individual to learn, including for elementary school students (Kuntarto & Prakash, 2020; Nafi'ah Setiani & Barokah, 2021). Digital literacy is a skill that students need to face the 21st century (Lavi et al., 2021; Rahayu & Mayasari, 2018). However, based on the initial test carried out in class IV at SDN Ujungrusi 03, SDN Tembok Kidul 01, SDN Tembok Banjaran 01 and SDN Ujungrusi 01 shows that students' digital literacy skills are still low. Students tend to use digital media as a means of entertainment rather than learning. Seeing the inequality that occurs, interesting learning media that can integrate technology in learning is needed.

One of the innovations that can be done to introduce digital literacy to elementary school-age children is to use digital storybooks as a learning medium. Digital learning media in the form of storybooks can improve students' digital literacy skills (Mastuti et al., 2020; Permatasari et al., 2022). The results of the study that have been conducted show that there was a significant increase in the average value of digital literacy in the experimental group compared to the control group. The experimental group was treated with the application of digital storybooks, while the control group used printed storybooks. Students in the experimental group showed better ability to access, analyze, and communicate information through digital media. Implementing digital storybooks into literacy activities significantly improves students' digital skills (Fitriyanti, 2021; Haslinda et al., 2022). Digital storybooks are learning media that combines technology with educational content. One of the key factors contributing to the increase in digital literacy is the interactive features of digital storybooks (Bilqish et al., 2023; Tsuei et al., 2020). Children are more interested and motivated to learn when texts are equipped with multimedia elements such as animations, sounds, and other interactive features (Nurhasanah et al., 2022; Wonda et al., 2022). To be able to use these features, learners must have skills in operating digital devices, understanding instructions, and following prescribed workflows (Cahyani & Jayanta, 2021; Getenet et al., 2024)

The experience of using digital storybooks helps students become more comfortable and confident in using technology (Rizkiyah, 2022; Yu & Zadorozhnyy, 2022). Students who often use digital books improve their digital literacy skills compared to students who use printed books (Jun, 2024; Shiyamsyah & Yuliani, 2022). This is because the intensity of the use of digital storybooks is proportional to digital literacy skills (Rosalina et al., 2021; Syah et al., 2019). By accessing and interacting with digital storybooks, learners can get used to operating digital devices, accessing digital content, and understanding how to use digital media effectively (Hendra et al., 2023; Rofiah et al., 2024). The strength of this research lies in the use of digital storybook learning media that is relevant to the condition of students as digital natives. The experimental approach used is also the strength of this study. The researcher measured the influence directly on the variables of reading interest and digital literacy. The instruments used have also gone through an adequate validation and reliability process, so that the results obtained can be trusted. Practically, this research provides innovations in integrating technology that can improve the quality of literacy learning. Teachers can make digital storybooks as an alternative learning media that can improve digital literacy skills from an early age. On the other hand, these findings also provide encouragement for schools to be more adaptive to technological developments through the provision of facilities and training that support digital literacy.

The findings of this study have several important implications for educational practice, curriculum development, and policy-making in the context of elementary education. First, the demonstrated effectiveness of digital storybooks in enhancing students' digital literacy underscores the need for schools to integrate more technology-based learning materials into early grade instruction. Teachers should be provided with adequate training and resources to effectively implement digital storybooks as part of their literacy and digital skills instruction. Moreover, curriculum developers should consider incorporating interactive digital content that aligns with students' developmental needs and learning outcomes in both language and digital competencies. At the policy level, educational authorities are encouraged to support the digital transformation of classrooms by ensuring equitable access to digital devices and high-quality educational content, thereby fostering inclusive and future-oriented learning environments. However, this study has some limitations. The duration of the study is relatively short, so it is not possible to evaluate the long-term impact on students' digital literacy skills. Control variables such as the influence of family support have not been analyzed in depth. Based on these limitations, it is suggested that future research involves more research objects with diverse backgrounds, and is carried out over a longer period of time. In addition, a mixed approach can be used to delve deeper into the experiences and perceptions of students and teachers in using digital storybooks as a learning medium.

4. CONCLUSION

The results of this study demonstrate that the integration of digital storybooks into elementary school learning significantly enhances students' digital literacy skills. Students who engaged with digital storybooks exhibited higher proficiency in navigating digital tools, understanding multimedia content, and demonstrating responsible digital behaviour compared to their peers who used traditional printed storybooks. The interactive features embedded in digital storybooks—such as audio narration, animations, and clickable elements—not only captured students' attention but also facilitated more active and autonomous learning experiences. These findings suggest that digital storybooks are not only a valuable resource for language development but also serve as an innovative medium for cultivating essential digital competencies from an early age. Therefore, incorporating digital storybooks into primary education curricula can be a strategic approach to prepare students for the demands of an increasingly digitalized world.

5. REFERENCES

- Abdullah, S., & Wicaksono, J. W. (2020). Urgensi pendidikan karakter berbasis literasi digital pada siswa SDN 39 kota ternate. *JPD: Jurnal Pendidikan Dasa*, 1, 1–20.
- Achmad, W. K. S., & Utami, U. (2023). Sense-making of digital literacy for future education era: a literature review. *Jurnal Prima Edukasia*, 11(1), 47–53. <https://doi.org/10.21831/jpe.v11i1.52911>.
- Achmadi, A., Akbar, G. R., Azizah, H., Fitria, Y., & Media, A. (2024). Peran Literasi Digital di Era Teknologi dalam Meningkatkan Kualitas Pendidikan di Era Teknologi. *Jurnal Ilmiah Kajian Multidisipliner*, 8(11), 147–153. <https://oaj.jurnalhst.com/index.php/jikm/article/view/6057>.
- Andhany, E., & Maysarah, S. (2023). Pengembangan Modul Pembelajaran Digital Interaktif Berbasis Literasi Matematika. *AKSIOMA: Jurnal Program Studi Pendidikan Matematika*, 12(3), 3503. <https://doi.org/10.24127/ajpm.v12i3.6299>.
- Andriyani, A., Djannah, S. N., Akmal, A., Aprilia, D. D., & Muhajir, M. (2023). Penguatan Literasi Digital Guru dan Siswa Sanggar Bimbingan Kampung Baru dan Kepong melalui Pembelajaran Holistik

- Berdiferensiasi Konten Digital. *Prima Abdika: Jurnal Pengabdian Masyarakat*, 3(4), 473–482. <https://doi.org/10.37478/abdika.v3i4.3413>.
- Anggraeni, H., Fauziyah, Y., & Fahyuni, E. F. (2019). Penguatan Blended Learning Berbasis Literasi Digital Dalam Menghadapi Era Revolusi Industri 4.0. *Al-Idarah : Jurnal Kependidikan Islam*, 9(2), 190–203. <https://doi.org/10.24042/alidarah.v9i2.5168>.
- Aoun, J. E. (2017). Robot-Proof. In *The MIT Press* (1st ed., Vol. 11, Issue 1). The MIT Press.
- Arikarani, Y., & Amirudin, M. F. (2021). Pemanfaatan Media dan Teknologi Digital Dalam Mengatasi Masalah Pembelajaran Dimasa Pandemi. *Ej*, 4(1), 93–116. <https://doi.org/10.37092/ej.v4i1.296>.
- Astriyandi, A. A. (2016). Pengembangan Buku Digital Interaktif Untuk Pemahaman Konsep Geografi. *Jurnal Geografi Gea*, 16(1), 13. <https://doi.org/10.17509/gea.v16i1.3464>.
- Bayu Ambarsari, T. A. (2023). Kesiapan Literasi Generasi Digital Natives Dalam Menghadapi Pendidikan Era Society 5.0. *Jurnal Inovasi Teknologi Dan Edukasi Teknik*, 3(7), 1. <https://doi.org/10.17977/um068.v3.i7.2023.1>.
- Beck, E., Goin, M. E., Ho, A., Parks, A., & Rowe, S. (2021). Critical digital literacy as method for teaching tactics of response to online surveillance and privacy erosion. *Computers and Composition*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compcom.2021.102654>.
- Bilqish, A., Damayanti, E., Harahap, I. S., Sakinah, N., & Batubara, R. A. (2023). Upaya meningkatkan minat baca siswa sekolah dasar melalui media pembelajaran berbasis e-bookstory. *Jurnal Riset Rumpun Ilmu Bahasa (JURRIBAH)*, 2(2). <https://doi.org/10.55606/jurribah.v2i2.1491>.
- Buckingham, D. (2020). Epilogue: Rethinking digital literacy: Media education in the age of digital capitalism. *Digital Education Review*, 37, 230–239. <https://doi.org/10.1344/der.2020.37.230-239>.
- Cahaya, U. D., Simarmata, J., Iwan, Suleman, N., Nisa, K., Nasbey, H., Muharlisiani, L. T., Karwanto, Putri, M. D., Chamidah, D., Pagiling, S. L., & Rahmadani, E. (2023). Inovasi pembelajaran berbasis digital abad 21. In *Penerbit Yayasan Kita Menulis*.
- Cahyani, N. L. aParamita, & Jayanta, I. N. L. (2021). Digital Literacy-Based Learning Video on the Topic of Natural Resources and Technology for Grade IV Elementary School. *Jurnal Ilmiah Sekolah Dasar*, 5(3), 538. <https://doi.org/10.23887/jisd.v5i3.37918>.
- Chan, B. S. K., Churchill, D., & Chiu, T. K. F. (2017). Digital Literacy Learning in Higher Education through Digital Storytelling Approach. *Journal of International Education Research (JIER)*, 13(1), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.19030/jier.v13i1.9907>.
- Devi Widiyanti, Dinda Fadila, Nita Pratiwi, & Ichsan Fauzi Rachman. (2024). Peran Literasi Digital Pada Siswa Sekolah Dasar Untuk Pencapaian Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 2030. *Morfologi: Jurnal Ilmu Pendidikan, Bahasa, Sastra Dan Budaya*, 2(3), 142–155. <https://doi.org/10.61132/morfologi.v2i3.626>.
- Djonov, E., Tseng, C. I., & Lim, F. V. (2021). Children's experiences with a transmedia narrative: Insights for promoting critical multimodal literacy in the digital age. *Discourse, Context and Media*, 43, 100493. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dcm.2021.100493>.
- Elsola, D. A. N., & Rochmiyati, S. (2023). Pemanfaatan media burita (buku cerita digital) untuk meningkatkan minat membaca siswa sd negeri selo. *Pendas : Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Dasar*, 27(2), 58–66. <https://doi.org/10.23969/jp.v8i3.10366>.
- Febliza, A., & Okatariyani, O. (2020). Pengembangan instrumen literasi digital sekolah, siswa dan guru. *Jurnal Pendidikan Kimia Universitas Riau*, 5(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.33578/jpk-unri.v5i1.7776>.
- Fitriyadi, N., & Wuryandani, W. (2021). Is educational game effective in improving critical thinking skills? *Jurnal Prima Edukasia*, 9(1), 107–117. <https://doi.org/10.21831/jpe.v9i1.35475>.
- Fitriyanti, P. (2021). Penggunaan E-Book Untuk Meningkatkan Minat Baca Siswa Sekolah Menengah Pertama. *Refleksi Edukatika : Jurnal Ilmiah Kependidikan*, 11(2), 170–177. <https://doi.org/10.24176/re.v11i2.5325>.
- Fraillon, J., Ainley, J., Schulz, W., Friedman, T., & Duckworth, D. (2020). Preparing for life in a digital world: IEA international computer and information literacy study 2018 international report. In *Preparing for Life in a Digital World: IEA International Computer and Information Literacy Study 2018 International Report*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-38781-5>.
- Gemala Qurbani, S. N. (2022). Penggunaan buku cerita bergambar elektronik interaktif di sekolah dasar. *Trihayu: Jurnal Pendidikan Ke-SD-An*, 9(1), 24–28. <https://doi.org/10.30738/trihayu.v9i1.13186>.
- Getenet, S., Cante, R., Redmond, P., & Albion, P. (2024). Students' digital technology attitude, literacy and self-efficacy and their effect on online learning engagement. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-023-00437-y>.
- Harjono, A., Makhrus, M., Savalas, L. R. T., & Rasmi, D. A. C. (2019). Pelatihan Pengembangan Perangkat Pembelajaran Ipa Untuk Mendukung Kesiapan Guru Sebagai Role Model Keterampilan Abad 21. *Jurnal Pendidikan Dan Pengabdian Masyarakat*, 2(3), 343–347. <https://doi.org/10.29303/jppm.v2i3.1345>.
- Haslinda, F., Maghfiroh, N., & Fadillah, S. R. (2022). Buku digital sebagai media pengembangan literasi.

- Seminar Nasional Ilmu Ilmu Sosial, Universitas Negeri Surabaya*, 576–584.
- Helsper, E. J., & Smahel, D. (2020). Excessive internet use by young Europeans: psychological vulnerability and digital literacy? *Information Communication and Society*, 23(9), 1255–1273. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2018.1563203>.
- Hendaryan, R., Hidayat, T., & Herliani, S. (2022). Pelaksanaan literasi digital dalam meningkatkan kemampuan literasi siswa. *Jurnal Literasi*, 6(April 2022), 142–151. <https://doi.org/10.25157/literasi.v6i1.7218>.
- Hendra, Afriyadi, H., Tanwir, Noor Hayati, Supardi, Laila, S. N., Prakasa, Y. F., Hasibuan, R. P. A., & Asyhar, A. D. A. (2023). Media Pembelajaran Berbasis Digital (Teori & Praktik). In *PT. Sonpedia Publishing Indonesia* (Issue 1).
- Hidayati, A., Efendi, R., & Saputra, A. (2020). The quality of digital literation early childhood education teachers based on Unesco standards. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, 9(3), 3514–3517.
- Islami, N. N., Wahyuni, S., & Puji, R. P. N. (2021). Digital literation of micro, small and medium enterprises (msmes) in jember district. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 747(1). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/747/1/012097>.
- Isma, C. N., Rina Rahmi, & Hanifuddin Jamin. (2022). Urgensi Digitalisasi Pendidikan Sekolah. *At-Ta'Dib: Jurnal Ilmiah Prodi Pendidikan Agama Islam*, 14(2), 129–141. <https://doi.org/10.47498/tadib.v14i2.1317>.
- Jauhari, C. R. M. (2021). *Pengembangan Buku Besar Berbasis Elektronik dalam Meningkatkan Keterampilan Membaca Awal Siswa Kelas II MIN 3 Aceh Barat*. UIN Ar-Raniry.
- Jun, H. (2024). *The effect of classes using digital materials in science classes on elementary school students' digital literacy and their perception of digital classes*. Affiliated Educational Research Institute of Seowon University College of Education. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.34245/jed.43.3.857>.
- Kuntarto, H. B., & Prakash, A. (2020). Digital Literacy Among Children in Elementary Schools. *Diakom : Jurnal Media Dan Komunikasi*, 3(2), 157–170. <https://doi.org/10.17933/diakom.v3i2.92>.
- Kurniawan, A. W., & Puspitaningtyas, Z. (2016). Metode penelitian kuantitatif. In *Pandiva Buku*.
- Lase, D. (2016). Pendidikan di Era Revolusi Industri 4.0 Education. *Journal Sunderman*, 1(1), 28–43. <https://doi.org/10.36588/sundermann.v1i1.18>.
- Lavi, R., Tal, M., & Dori, Y. J. (2021). Perceptions of STEM alumni and students on developing 21st century skills through methods of teaching and learning. *Studies in Educational Evaluation*, 70, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.stueduc.2021.101002>.
- Liang, Q., Torre, J. de la, & Law, N. (2021). Do background characteristics matter in Children's mastery of digital literacy? A cognitive diagnosis model analysis. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2021.106850>.
- Mardiana, S., Annisarizki, Marthalena, Liza Diniarizky Putri, & Sigit Surahman. (2022). Literasi Digital dalam Upaya Mendukung Pembelajaran Online pada Siswa Sekolah Dasar di Kota Cilegon. *KAIBON ABHINAYA: JURNAL PENGABDIAN MASYARAKAT*, 4(1), 47–54. <https://doi.org/10.30656/ka.v4i1.3809>.
- Marsh, J. (2016). The Digital Literacy Skills and Competences of Children of Pre-School Age. *Media Education*, 7(2), 197–214. <https://doi.org/10.14605/MED721603>.
- Mastuti, R., Maulana, S., Iqbal, M., Faried, A. I., Arpan, Hasibuan, A. F. H., Jamaludin, Wirapraja, A., Saputra, D. H., Sugianto, Jamaludin, Arifah, F. N., Pinem, W., Purnomo, A., Saragih, L. M. S., Napitupulu, D., Hastuti, P., Tasnim, & Vinolina, N. S. (2020). Teaching from home dari belajar merdeka menuju merdeka belajar. In *Yayasan Kita Menulis* (1st ed., Vol. 6, Issue 1). Yayasan Kita Menulis.
- Moore, H. T. D., & Trysnes, I. (2021). Kindergarteners building a library of their own: Using apps to make digital stories and work towards lifelong learning in information literacy. *Journal of Information Literacy*, 15(3), 4–19. <https://doi.org/10.11645/15.3.2825>.
- Mukhlisina, I., & Danawati, M. G. (2023). Analisis Literasi Digital Dalam Pembelajaran Pada Siswa Kelas Iii Sd Muhammadiyah 8 Malang. *Inventa*, 7(1), 63–77. <https://doi.org/10.36456/inventa.7.1.a7029>.
- Nafi'ah Setiani, N., & Barokah, N. (2021). Urgensi literasi digital dalam menyongsong siswa sekolah dasar menuju generasi emas tahun 2045. *Prosiding SEMAI Seminar Nasional PGMI 2021*, 411–427.
- Naila, I., Ridlwan, M., & Haq, M. A. (2021). Literasi digital bagi guru dan siswa sekolah dasar: analisis konten dalam pembelajaran. *Jurnal Review Pendidikan Dasar*, 7(2), 116–122. <https://doi.org/10.26740/jrpd.v7n2.p166-122>.
- Naimah, Muhammad Fauzan Muttaqin, & Meilina. (2024). Implementasi Literasi Digital pada Siswa Sekolah Dasar. *Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Profesi Guru*, 7(1), 85–94. <https://doi.org/10.23887/jippg.v7i1.75992>.
- Nasrullah, R., Aditya, W., Satya, T. I., Nento, M. N., Hanifah, N., Miftahussururi, & Akbari, Q. S. (2017). Materi Pendukung Literasi Digital. In *Kementerian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan*.
- Neumann, M. M., & Merchant, G. (2022). "That's a Big Bad Wolf!": Learning through Teacher-Child Talk

- During Shared Reading of a Story Book App. *Early Childhood Education Journal*, 50(3), 515–525. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10643-021-01171-8>.
- Nisa, N., Arum, N., Hidayat, S. N., & Wahyuningsih, Y. (2023). Penguatan Pendidikan Karakter melalui Literasi Digital di Sekolah Dasar. *Journal on Education*, 05(02), 2457–2464. <https://jonedu.org/index.php/joe/article/view/908>.
- Nurchaili. (2016). Menumbuhkan budaya literasi melalui buku digital. *LIBRIA*, 8, 197–209. <https://doi.org/10.22373/libria.8.2>.
- Nurdina, R. A. (2022). Pengaruh pemanfaatan media pembelajaran digital titration screen experiment terhadap literasi digital dan hasil belajar siswa kelas xi sma n 1 surakarta pada materi titrasi asam basa. In *UNS* (Issue 8.5.2017). Universitas Sebelas Maret.
- Nurfaizah, N., Hermanto, N., Wibowo, A. T., Fathuzaen, F., & Rozaq, H. A. A. (2022). Implementasi Aplikasi Baca dan Tulis Sebagai Upaya Peningkatan Literasi Digital. *Paradigma - Jurnal Komputer Dan Informatika*, 24(1), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.31294/paradigma.v24i1.928>.
- Nurhasanah, Yunita, D., Fansyuri, M., Khoirunnissya, & Tassia, E. (2022). Pemanfaatan Buku Digital Untuk Meningkatkan Minat Baca Anak dan Balita. *Jurnal Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat Universitas Pamulang*, 3(1), 53–61.
- Nurhayati, D. (2017). Pengembangan buku digital interaktif mata kuliah pengembangan e-learning pada mahasiswa teknologi pendidikan fip uny. In *Journal of Chemical Information and Modeling* (Vol. 53, Issue 9). Universitas Negeri Yogyakarta.
- Nurjanah, E., Rusmana, A., & Yanto, A. (2017). Hubungan Literasi Digital dengan Kualitas Penggunaan E-Resources. *Lentera Pustaka: Jurnal Kajian Ilmu Perpustakaan, Informasi Dan Kearsipan*, 3(2), 117. <https://doi.org/10.14710/lenpust.v3i2.16737>.
- Pangrazio, L., Godhe, A. L., & Ledesma, A. G. L. (2020). What is digital literacy? A comparative review of publications across three language contexts. *E-Learning and Digital Media*, 17(6), 442–459. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2042753020946291>.
- Permatasari, A. D., Iftitah, K. N., Sugiarti, Y., & Anwas, E. O. M. (2022). Peningkatan literasi indonesia melalui buku elektronik. *Kwangsan: Jurnal Teknologi Pendidikan*, 10(2), 261. <https://doi.org/10.31800/jtp.kw.v10n2.p261--282>.
- Polizzi, G. (2020). Digital Literacy and the National Curriculum for England: Learning from how the experts engage with and evaluate online content. *Computers & Education*, 152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2020.103859>.
- Putu, L., & Arima, S. (2024). Peran literasi digital dalam meningkatkan kompetensi teknologi siswa sekolah dasar. *Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Citra Bakti*, 11, 1255–1267. <https://doi.org/10.38048/jipcb.v11i4.4681>.
- Rahayu, T., & Mayasari, T. (2018). Profil kemampuan awal literasi digital dalam pembelajaran fisika siswa SMK Kota Madiun. *Seminar Nasional Quantum*, 25, 431.
- Rawung, W. H., Katuuk, D. A., Rotty, V. N. J., & Lengkong, J. S. J. (2021). Kurikulum dan Tantangannya pada Abad 21. *Jurnal Bahana Manajemen Pendidikan*, 10(1), 29. <https://doi.org/10.24036/jbmp.v10i1.112127>.
- Reddy, P., Sharma, B., & Chaudhary, K. (2020). Digital literacy: A review of literature. In *International Journal of Technoethics*. <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJT.20200701.oa1>.
- Rizkiyah, P. (2022). Pengembangan buku cerita bergambar berbasis digital untuk meningkatkan kecakapan literasi digital anak usia dini. *Indonesian Journal of Early Childhood: Jurnal Dunia Anak Usia Dini*, 4(1), 115. <https://doi.org/10.35473/ijec.v4i1.1230>.
- Rochmiyati, S., Tiasari, L., & Ermawati. (2024). Promoting Character Education Through Genre-Based Language Learning: A Digital Reading Box in the Spotlight. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 14(3), 813–820. <https://doi.org/10.17507/tpls.1403.23>.
- Rofiah, N. H., Restiana, R., & Dewi, R. (2024). Promoting digital literacy: assessing teachers readiness in utilizing information and communication technology for learning in rural area. *Jurnal Prima Edukasia*, 12(1), 41–51. <https://doi.org/10.21831/jpe.v12i1.63968>.
- Roll, M. J. J., & Ifenthaler, D. (2021). Multidisciplinary digital competencies of pre-service vocational teachers. *Empirical Research in Vocational Education and Training*, 13(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40461-021-00112-4>.
- Rosalina, D., Yuliari, K., Setianingsih, D., & Zati, M. R. (2021). Faktor-faktor yang berpengaruh terhadap kompetensi literasi digital mahasiswa di era revolusi industri 4.0. *EKONIKA Jurnal Ekonomi Universitas Kadiri*, 6(2), 294. <https://doi.org/10.30737/ekonika.v6i2.1996>.
- Setiawan, A., Lukmanulhakim, L., & Linarsih, A. (2023). Efektivitas Gerakan Literasi Digital Di Sekolah Jenjang Pendidikan Dasar Di Kota Pontianak. *Jurnal Visi Ilmu Pendidikan*, 15(1), 102. <https://doi.org/10.26418/jvip.v15i1.60994>.
- Shiyamsyah, F. S. F., & Yuliani, Y. (2022). Pengembangan e-book interaktif pada materi respirasi seluler untuk melatih kemampuan literasi digital siswa sma kelas xii. *Berkala Ilmiah Pendidikan Biologi*

- (*BioEdu*), 11(2), 492–501. <https://doi.org/10.26740/bioedu.v11n2.p492-501>.
- Sinaga, A. V. (2023). Peranan Teknologi dalam Pembelajaran untuk Membentuk Karakter dan Skill Peserta Didik Abad 21. *Journal on Education*, 06(01), 2836–2846. <http://jonedu.org/index.php/joe>.
- Solfiah, Y. S., Risma, D., Hukmi, & Kurnia, R. (2020). Early childhood disaster management media through picture story books. *JPUJ - Jurnal Pendidikan Usia Dini*, 14(1), 141–155. <https://doi.org/10.21009/141.10>.
- Syah, R., Darmawan, D., & Purnawan, A. (2019). Analisis faktor yang mempengaruhi kemampuan literasi digital. *Jurnal AKRAB*, 10(2), 60–69. <https://doi.org/10.51495/jurnalakrab.v10i2.290>.
- Toharudin, M., Sari, H. K., Pranoto, B. A., & Fitri, R. M. (2021). Budaya literasi dan literasi digital di sekolah dasar. *PijIES Pedagogik Journal of Islamic Elementary School*, 4(2), 175–190. <https://doi.org/10.24256/pijies.v4i2.2916>.
- Tsuei, M., Huang, H. W., & Cheng, S. F. (2020). The effects of a peer-tutoring strategy on children's e-book reading comprehension. *South African Journal of Education*, 40(2), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.15700/saje.v40n2a1734>.
- Urip Umayah, & Riwanto, M. A. (2020). Transformasi Sekolah Dasar abad 21 New Digital Literacy untuk Membangun Karakter Siswa di Era Global. *JURNAL PANCAR (Pendidik Anak Cerdas Dan Pintar)*, 4(1), 1–10. <https://ejournal.unugha.ac.id/index.php/pancar/article/view/308>.
- Utami, D. S., & Asri Hardini, A. T. (2021). Pengembangan Media Belajar Literasi Digital Berbasis Game Edukasi untuk Siswa Kelas 2 SD. *JIKAP PGSD: Jurnal Ilmiah Ilmu Kependidikan*, 5(2), 218. <https://doi.org/10.26858/jkp.v5i2.20162>.
- Wangid, M. N., Putra, C. A., & Rudyanto, H. E. (2021). The Science-Math Stories Based on Digital Learning: Digital Literacy Innovation in Increasing Ability to Solve Problems. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 16(9), 94–107. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v16i09.22039>.
- Widiputera, F. (2021). Profil kompetensi digital siswa di indonesia. In *Puslitjak, Balitbang & Perbukuan Kemdikbud*.
- Wijaya, E. Y., Sudjimat, D. A., & Nyoto, A. (2016). Transformasi Pendidikan Abad 21 Sebagai Tuntutan. *Jurnal Pendidikan*, 1, 263–278.
- Wilson, M., Scalise, K., & Gochyyev, P. (2018). Learning in digital networks as a modern approach to ict literacy. *Springer International Publishing*, 181–210. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-65368-6_11.
- Wonda, H., Kota, M. K., & Arianti, C. D. (2022). Pengembangan buku digital sebagai media untuk meningkatkan motivasi belajar siswa kelas iv. *Primary: Jurnal Pendidikan Guru Sekolah Dasar*, 11(6), 1751. <https://doi.org/10.33578/jpfkip.v11i6.9115>.
- Wrahatnolo, T., & Munoto. (2018). 21st centuries skill implication on educational system. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 296(1). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/296/1/012036>.
- Wusqo, I. U., Khusniati, M., Pamelasari, S. D., Laksono, A., & Wulandari, D. (2021). The effectiveness of digital science scrapbook on students' science visual literacy. *Jurnal Pendidikan IPA Indonesia*, 10(1), 121–126. <https://doi.org/10.15294/jpii.v10i1.27130>.
- Xiang, J., & Yan, Y. (2020). Mutual promotion of reading and expression: research into children's picture book teaching of i wanna iguana. *International Dialogues on Education Journal*, 7(2), 60–69. <https://doi.org/10.53308/ide.v7i2.37>.
- Yefanov, A. A., Budanova, M. A., & Yudina, E. N. (2020). Digital literacy of schoolchildren and teachers: A comparative analysis. *RUDN Journal of Sociology*. <https://doi.org/10.22363/2313-2272-2020-20-2-382-393>.
- Yu, B., & Zadorozhnyy, A. (2022). Developing students' linguistic and digital literacy skills through the use of multimedia presentations. *ReCALL*, 34(1), 95–109. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0958344021000136>.
- Yusniati, B. K. P., Musaddat, S., & Hakim, M. (2023). Analisis Keterampilan Literasi Digital Siswa Kelas V Sdn 1 Rarang Selatan Tahun Ajaran 2022/2023. *Pendas: Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Dasar*, 08(September), 89–90. <https://doi.org/10.23969/jp.v8i2.9264>.
- Zaidi, R., Metcalfe, R., & Norton, B. (2022). Dual Language Books Go Digital: Storybooks Canada in French Immersion Schools and Homes. *Canadian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 25(1), 64–87. <https://doi.org/10.37213/cjal.2022.31626>.
- Zipke, M. (2017). Preschoolers explore interactive storybook apps: The effect on word recognition and story comprehension. *Education and Information Technologies*, 22(4), 1695–1712. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-016-9513-x>.